

Physico-chemical interpretation and evidence for the aero-tolerance of obligate anaerobes, a natural environmental phenomena

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Abstract : Methanogens, acetogens and sulfate reducing bacteria are known as obligate anaerobes and ubiquitous in nature. They are believed not to survive in presence of air or oxygen, oxygen for their metabolism or growth usually comes from oxygen containing inorganic salts. Methane emission from rice paddy soils or by methanogens or acetogens in a synthetic broth medium in presence of limited supply of oxygen suggest that methanogens, acetogens are capable of sustaining in limited supply of oxygen by an environmental adaptation. Methanogenic activities of formate reducing methanogens isolated from local habitats in Breznak AC21 medium under oxic, partially oxic and anoxic conditions also suggest that methanogens have the capability of metabolic response and oxygen tolerance in limited supply of oxygen. No convincing mechanism of exhibiting aero-tolerance by the anaerobes has been suggested.

A physico-chemical mechanism for the phenomenon of aero-tolerance of anaerobes has been put forward. Methanogenesis or other anaerobic activities are usually carried out under reducing conditions and at pH near or above 7. Under the conditions of the experiment, O₂ is usually converted to OH⁻ in limited supply of O₂.

The oxidation of anaerobic ponds shows initial increase of pH on passing O₂ for purification of water in anaerobic ponds which corroborates the physico-chemical mechanism of aerotolerance of anaerobes like methanogens.

Keywords : AC21 medium, aero-tolerance, anaerobic ponds, DO, methane emission, methanogen, microaerophily, physico-chemical interpretation, rice-cultivating soils.

Introduction

Aerobes and anaerobes are ubiquitous in nature and are abundant in soils. Obligate anaerobes like cellulolytic bacteria, sulphate reducing bacteria and methane producing bacteria, are supposed not to survive in air or O₂. In reality, they survive in presence of air or O₂ as observed in case of rice paddy soils which are dry and perched during summer but they work during rainy season and during rice paddy cultivation. The activities of anaerobes are restricted in absence of water but they derive O₂ for their metabolic activities *in situ* from inorganic minerals containing O₂ or even from little water. It shows that the survival of anaerobes in air is an environmental process

of adaptation and self-defense against O₂ for the anaerobes. The production of methane during the rice paddy cultivation or even in presence of sufficient amount of water, C, N, and under optimum pH and temperatures suggest the survival of methanogens and other anaerobes is a natural environmental process. But the proper explanation is lacking. Biogas generation and the different aspects of biogas generation including microbial aspects and pilot scale production of biogas had been systematically studied by Lahiri and co-workers¹⁻¹⁴. In a previous paper, Chakraborty *et al.*⁶ reported aero-tolerance of methanogens but no proper explanation for aero-tolerance could be made. *In vitro* methane emissions from different

rice paddy soils and algal mats were studied under anoxic and limited oxic or atmospheric conditions. Methane production from rice paddy soils cultivating different strains of rice was found to be appreciable under anoxic conditions but considerably reduced under atmospheric conditions. The methane emission is dependent on rice cultivars (strains) as will be apparent from the Table 1 and in general, the cultivars producing more rice emit less methane.

Table 1. Rice cultivars and soil methane production sensitivity under atmospheric condition

Rice cultivars	% Reduction of methane (after 30 days)
Jhingisal	15.3
Pankaj	23.7
Minikit	20.8
Chamanmoni	19.3
Swarna	77.2
Br II	100.0
Spirogyra mat	53.3

The results indicated that methanogens though strict anaerobes, can sustain in presence of limited supply of O₂, i.e. methanogens are aero-tolerant or microaerophilic with restricted catabolism. The results from algal mats corroborated these findings.

The results were further substantiated from the study of the methanogenic activities of formate reducing methanogens isolated from different natural habitats under oxic and anoxic conditions^{2-6,8-14}.

Materials and methods :

The H₂/CO₂ (80 : 20) utilizing methanogens namely TDM (methanogen from sewage disposal plant, Calcutta), TRM (methanogen from tannery refuses at Tangra, Calcutta) and PMW (methanogen from paper mill wastes, Chakdah), collected and cultivated in our laboratory were used^{2,9-12}.

Optimization of conditions for production of methane :

The isolation of methanogens and their culture were described before^{2,9-11}. Methanogens were isolated from three different sources following the modified roll-tube technique described by Millar and Wolin¹⁵ using Breznak AC21 medium^{16,9-11}. Before inoculation, 1.25% w/v, g/l cysteine HCl (final concentration) was added as reductant

and the pH of the Breznak AC21 medium was adjusted with dilute Na₂CO₃ solution. Na₂S.9H₂O was not added to the medium to avoid reaction with metals and cysteine HCl was the sole reductant. There was no effect on the growth of the methanogen due to a lack of Na₂S.9H₂O. Methane obtained from serially diluted AC21 medium after 2 weeks of cultivation was used. The isolation was done in presence of ampicillin (1000 µg/ml) from the serial dilution vials, the culture diluted to 10⁻³ exhibited methanogenesis. The culture was subsequently diluted serially ten times in AC21 medium. The cells of isolated methanogens were slender, crooked rods with blunt, rounded ends. Cells were long and often formed chains. Cells were found to be of varying size (0.3 to 0.8 µm wide and 2 to 13 µm long), flat, non-motile, non-endospore forming. Surface colonies of the microbes were gray and flat and the microbes used H₂/CO₂, sodium formate, sodium bicarbonate, casamino acids and yeast extract as C-sources for growth. According to the characterization, strain TDM, TRM and PMW methanogens were identified as *Methanobacterium formicicum*^{2,9-11}. The purity of the cultures was checked repeatedly microscopically using an Olympus BHS microscope. The rate of production of methane appeared to be slow and required about 20 days to record maximum values. The progressive yield efficiency (cell/time) as obtained from maximum probable number of methanogen per milliliter broth medium were in the range of 10-999, 12-885 and 10-568 for TDM, TRM and PMW methanogens respectively for a period of 5-20 days at 37 °C.

Growth was examined at temperatures ranging from 4 to 70 °C, and pHs varying from 4 to 9. The optimum temperature for methane production had been found to be around 37 °C suggesting the mesophilic nature of microbes. The methanogens incubated in methanogenic medium at 4 °C and 10 °C produced no methane.

The optimum pH for maximum methane production was found to be 7.2 ± 0.2, from the observation of methane production of the microbes under varying pH (by suitable addition of dilute HCl or NaOH in the broth medium). The methane production was almost zero at pH 5 but the methanogens did not survive at pH 4. Therefore, the subsequent experiments were optimized and carried out at pH 7.2 ± 0.2 and at 37 °C.

Production of methane in absence and presence of O₂ or under atmospheric conditions :

Actively growing log phase cultures namely TDM, TRM and PMW methanogens in AC21 medium (50 ml in 125 ml anaerobic serum vials) were used as inocula. The experiments were carried out aseptically under strict anaerobic conditions (in Argon atmosphere), in partially oxic condition (by volume to volume replacement of Argon by Aolar oxygen and in aerobic condition in absence of Argon).

All the experimental set ups were incubated for 20 days at 37 °C and maintained at pH 7.2 or slightly above.

Methane evolved within the vials under different conditions was analyzed gas chromatographically (Table 2).

Instruments and measurements :

Methane concentrations in the gas samples in different vials were quantified as a function of time using a Netel gas chromatograph (Model Omega QC, India) fitted with Flame Ionization Detector (FID) and silica gel methane column (80/20 mesh). The column, injector and detector temperature was maintained at 70, 130 and 130 °C respectively. Carrier gas was nitrogen, with a flow rate of 30 ml/min. Hydrogen was used as the fuel gas and zero air as the supporting gas, having flow rates of 25 and 250 ml/min respectively. Concentration of CH₄ in a sample was determined in the way described

before^{2,9-12,14}. Other gases were obtained from the Indian Oxygen Co. Ltd (Kolkata, India).

Systronics digital pH meter with reproducibility of 0.01 units was used for pH-measurements.

The chemicals used were of highest purity from Sigma Chemicals (USA), Oxoid Ltd. (England) and E. Merck (Germany). The results, the average of triplicate sets of measurements are presented in the Tables 2a and 2b. The isolates are gram positive and have catalase activity i.e. have the ability to quench toxic forms of O₂ like H₂O₂ and organic peroxides.

Results and discussion

The results from the biomethanation experiments show that methanogens though obligate anaerobes can tolerate limited supply of O₂ (Table 2). The capacity of so-called

Table 2a. Growth spectrum of different isolated methanogens under aerobic (i.e. without Argon atmosphere) and anaerobic condition (in parenthesis)

Methanogen	%CH ₄ yield at different time intervals (× 24 h)							
	7	12	14	16	18	20	25	30
TRM	1.7 (16.3)	4.8 (36.6)	8.3 (38.8)	10.9 (40.6)	16.6 (55.1)	12.2 (49.3)	10.2 (41.3)	9.8 (39.9)
TDM	1.3 (13.6)	7.9 (39.1)	12.1 (41.5)	14.4 (44.1)	19.3 (55.4)	20.3 (52.7)	12.1 (50.9)	7.4 (42.8)
PMW	2.4 (10.9)	5.1 (18.1)	7.8 (27.2)	13.4 (34.5)	19.4 (40.8)	20.1 (43.3)	11.4 (38.8)	5.5 (37.2)

Table 2b. Growth spectrum of isolated methanogens under different oxygen tension

Methanogen	[O] (i.e. O ₂ concn.)	%CH ₄ yield at different time intervals (× 24 h)						
		6	8	10	12	14	16	18
TRM	A. Control (Argon atmosphere)	16.6	20.8	29.9	37.5	48.8	50.9	55.5
	B. 10% (O ₂)	7.3	16.1	18.5	26.3	29.1	45.8	45.8
	C. 20% (O ₂)	-	9.9	11.7	12.5	28.1	34.7	40.8
	D. 30% (O ₂)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
TDM	A. Control (Argon atmosphere)	15.3	17.9	29.9	48.1	50.5	52.1	56.6
	B. 10% (O ₂)	11.1	15.4	18.8	28.3	30.1	37.7	38.9
	C. 20% (O ₂)	2.5	3.9	7.8	16.4	18.9	25.5	26.1
	D. 30% (O ₂)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PMW	A. Control (Argon atmosphere)	9.4	10.9	11.7	15.2	26.3	37.2	40.8
	B. 10% (O ₂)	5.5	7.8	8.1	12.1	18.5	26.3	36.1
	C. 20% (O ₂)	-	-	4.0	6.9	13.8	20.2	31.9
	D. 30% (O ₂)	-	-	-	-	5.1	10.4	11.0

strict anaerobes to tolerate and consume trace levels of O₂ was first demonstrated in case of sulphate reducing bacteria *Desulfovibrio* species which is considered to be a potentially oxygen reducing anaerobe found in termite gut microbiota¹⁷.

Tolerance and metabolic response of strict anaerobe acetogens towards oxygen were reported by Karnholz *et al.*¹⁸. Acetogens have anoxic habitats and utilize a pathway (the acetyl coenzyme A pathway) that contains enzymes that are extremely sensitive to O₂^{18,19}. However, evidences are there to indicate that acetogens :

(i) isolated from leaf litter and the mineral soil of well-drained, oxic soils can tolerate periods of oxygenation in soils^{20,21},

(ii) are active in termite gut that have steep O-gradients²² and

(iii) occur in high numbers in transiently oxygenated rhizosphere sediments colonized by sea grass²³.

These obviously suggest that certain acetogens must cope with O₂ under *in situ* conditions. The classic acetogen *Moorella thermoacetica* was reported to reduce resazurin in O₂-supplied medium. The acetogens (*Sporomusa silvacetica*, *Moorella thermoacetica*, *Clostridium magnum*, *Acetobacterium woodii* and *Thermoacetobacter kionii*) (i) grew in both semisolid and liquid cultivation media containing O₂ and (ii) consumed low amounts of O₂ causing a lag phase in growth but these acetogens have the ability to synthesize acetate via the acetyl co-enzyme pathway¹⁸.

Mannistii and Puhakka²⁴ reported 39 psychrotolerant and microaerophilic bacteria of different phylogenetic origin in cold (6–8 °C) and oxygen deficient ground water. In semisolid glucose and 59%, of the isolates respectively preferred microaerophilic growth and 33% were catalase negative. The microaerophilic isolates had the highest sensitivity to H₂O₂ whereas sensitivity to super oxide generator paraquat was similar among microaerophilic and aerobic isolates.

Biomethanation under oxic or atmospheric conditions²⁵ is possible as is evident from the works of Wimpeny and Abdollahi²⁶ who consider metabolic coupling of anaerobes and aerobes render co-existence of methanogens with aerobes possible. Gerritse and Gotschal²⁷ considered co-existence of methanogenic and aerobic bacteria

in oxygen limited ideal chemostats like soil where CH₄ production can occur in presence of O₂ suggesting the aero-tolerance in methanogens. Sensitivity to O₂ for methanogenic bacteria from rice paddy soils was reported by Fetzer *et al.*²⁸. The methanogens were found to survive oxic periods. They observed that the potential bacterial activity to produce CH₄ decreased with time of oxygen exposure exhibiting a residual activity about 25% though the viability of bacteria did not decrease. The observation had been found to be true whether the methanogen was obtained from a culture collection (*M. barkerii* strain Fusaro) or freshly isolated from a dry oxic paddy soil (*Methanosarcina* strain and *Methanobacterium* strain). Exposure periods (< 30 h) allowed 90% survival of the methanogenic species.

The aero-tolerance or microaerophily in anaerobes are known e.g. *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Wolinella recta* etc.²⁹.

Microaerophily in methanogens may be due to the possession of some enzymic self defense against O₂-toxicity^{30,31}. Moreover, in the scale of evolution, adaptive changes for aero-tolerance may be likely for obligate anaerobes like methanogen.

Molecular oxygen is associated both to aerobes and anaerobes but they have different methods of O₂-utilization³².

Many oxygen-tolerant anaerobes are well adapted to survive oxygen stress. Strict anaerobes have been suggested to maintain a functional energy metabolism in presence of or even based on molecular oxygen.

It is known that O₂ is converted into highly active radical O₂ + e → O₂⁻ (catalyzed by oxidases like aldehyde oxidase, NaDPH oxidase etc.) which is converted to harmless O₂ by the reaction

i.e. organisms or cells containing super oxide dimutase are able to tolerate O₂ or they are aero-tolerant (Schlegel, 1995).

However, cell extracts of aero-tolerant bacteria like *S. silvacetica*, *M. thermoacetica* and *C. magnum* though contained peroxidase and NADH oxidase activities but catalase and super oxide dimutase activities were not detected.

In spite of adducing any real proof and specific reason for aero-tolerance, the reasons forwarded are :

- (i) some enzymic self-defense against O-toxicity,
- (ii) presence of dimutase 9 though not found in many cases,
- (iii) metabolic coupling between aerobes and anaerobes in ideal chemostats and
- (iv) adaptability to survive oxygen stress.

These may be the reasons but the real reason for adaptability is physico-chemical. In anaerobiosis, a reducing condition must prevail. Degradation of polymeric units gives acetic acid (in 70% cases of methanogenesis), propionic acid, formic acid etc. and they are ultimately converted to CO₂ and H₂. In reducing conditions and in presence of H₂ at relatively high pH (> 6), both O₂ and CO₂ compete for reduction as follows :

O₂ is more powerful electron acceptor than CO₂ and O₂ reduction is highly favorable. Initially, under low O₂ concentration, O₂ will be completely converted to OH⁻ via reaction (2) and (3) leading to the increase in pH of the system keeping the system anaerobic and favorable for CH₄ via reaction (1), but with increase in O₂ concentration, anaerobic or reducing condition will be replaced by aerobic condition so that methanogenesis or other anaerobic process will be inhibited leading to the aerobic oxidation of the substrates. Under aerobic conditions all the reactions (1-3) will be hindered.

The fact is corroborated from the results of aeration (Table 3) of the anaerobic ponds (in sewage treatment plants). The initial DO values of water in ponds are 0 and pH < 7.00. But with gradual aeration, pH increases and reaches the maximal and DO levels gradually increase due to the replacement of anaerobic condition by aerobic oxidation. Thus, limited oxygen tolerance in the anaerobic processes are simply due to conversion of O₂ into OH⁻. It is known that both aerobes and anaerobes are ubiquitous in nature.

Anaerobes can sustain limited supply of O₂ and ultimately takes part in methane production during rice paddy cultivation. The aero-tolerance is also observed in the

Table 3. Result of oxidation for anaerobic ponds

Date	Raw sewage		Final pond outlet	
	pH	DO (mg/L)	pH	DO (mg/L)
25.10.99	7.09	0	8.36	6.91
03.11.99	7.08	0	8.09	7.34
26.11.99	7.02	0	7.94	6.29
09.12.99	7.68	0	8.33	6.24
29.12.99	7.21	0	7.81	6.48
20.01.00	7.14	0	7.87	6.09
25.01.00	7.03	0	8.11	6.45
08.02.00	6.75	0	7.91	6.58
23.02.00	6.86	0	8.06	6.01
08.03.00	7.11	0	7.73	5.98
19.03.00	7.16	0	7.98	6.19
10.04.00	7.17	0	7.71	5.89
05.05.00	7.24	0	7.92	6.31
19.05.00	7.22	0	7.89	5.86
07.06.00	7.12	0	7.92	5.82
21.06.00	7.19	0	7.97	5.88
12.07.00	7.05	0	7.89	6.72
21.07.00	7.01	0	8.21	6.35
11.08.00	7.09	0	7.97	7.42
24.08.00	7.31	0	7.85	6.59
11.09.00	7.17	0	7.87	6.35
10.10.00	7.15	0	7.73	6.18
09.11.00	7.01	0	8.03	5.77

initial phases of biomethanation in anaerobic digesters where dissolved O₂ in water and free void space above substrates contain sufficient amount of O₂ (air).

Anaerobic processes and associated biomethanation initially require a long time (more than three weeks) to utilize dissolved O₂ present in the digester and displace air from the free void space. But once air is displaced, biomethanation is relatively a rapid process.

The facts also corroborate that aero-tolerance in a physico-chemical process.

Conclusion :

Methane production from rice cultivating soils or by methanogens in methanogenic broth medium in presence of limited supply of oxygen is a physico-chemical phenomenon where in limited supply of oxygen, O₂ is converted to OH⁻. The fact is substantiated from the increase in DO and pH of water of the anaerobic ponds with aeration. The pH increases up to a certain limit after which conversion of O₂ to OH⁻ is not possible.

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